

The Shah Bano Case: A Fight for Dignity and Maintenance

Have you ever wondered how powerful words can be—powerful enough to end a lifetime relationship?

For many years, three simple utterances—talaq, talaq, talaq—were enough to dissolve a marriage under Muslim Personal Law. No warning, no discussion, no chance to respond—just words spoken or written, and a marriage of years comes to an end. For many Muslim women, this was not just a religious practice but a harsh reality under Muslim Personal Law.

The concept of Triple talaq also known as Talaq-ul-biddat, is a form of divorce that was practised in Islam, whereby a Muslim man could legally divorce his wife by pronouncing talaq three times. The man did not need to cite any cause for the divorce and the wife need not have been present at the time of pronouncement. But the case of Mohd. Ahmad Khan vs Shah Bano Begum & Ors. 1985 AIR 945, 1985 SCR (3) 844, also known as the Shah Bano case, is witnessed as one of the milestones in the history when a women refuses to accept the silence and knocks the door of justice and asked for basic maintenance.

Facts of the case

Mohd. Ahmed Khan, a lawyer by profession, married Shah Bano Begum in 1932. The couple had five children—three sons and two daughters. After more than four decades of marriage, Shah Bano Begum was abandoned by her husband in 1975, when she was 62 years old, and was forced to leave her matrimonial home along with her children. Facing financial hardship, Shah Bano Begum filed an application in 1978 before the Judicial Magistrate of First Class, Indore, seeking monthly maintenance of ₹500 under [Section 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code \(CrPC\)](#), a provision meant to prevent destitution.

During the pendency of the proceedings, Mohd. Ahmed Khan pronounced an irrevocable triple talaq and claimed that he was no longer liable to maintain her, as their marital relationship had ended. He further stated that he had already paid ₹200 per month as maintenance for nearly two years and had deposited ₹3,000 as dower (mehr) during the iddat period, thereby fulfilling his obligations under Muslim Personal Law. In 1979, the Magistrate directed the husband to pay ₹25 per month as maintenance to Shah Bano Begum. Dissatisfied with the inadequate amount, Shah Bano Begum filed a revision petition before the Madhya Pradesh High Court in 1980, which enhanced the maintenance to ₹179 per month. Aggrieved by the High Court's decision, Mohd. Ahmed Khan challenged the order before the Supreme Court of India by filing

a Special Leave Petition, leading to one of the most significant judgments in Indian legal history.

Issues of the case

1. Whether a divorced Muslim woman is entitled to claim maintenance under Section 125 CrPC, and whether the term “wife” under this provision includes a divorced Muslim woman who is unable to maintain herself
2. Whether a Muslim husband is legally bound under Section 125 CrPC to provide maintenance to his divorced wife, even if Muslim Personal Law limits his responsibility to the iddat period.
3. Whether the amount paid as mahr or dower can be treated as a “sum payable on divorce” under Section 127(3)(b) CrPC, and whether such payment can exempt the husband from further maintenance obligations.
4. Whether Section 125 of the CrPC applies to Muslim women, or whether they are excluded from its scope because they are governed by Muslim Personal Law.

What is Iddat?

Iddat refers to the mandatory waiting period that a Muslim woman is required to observe after the death of her husband or after divorce, before she can remarry. The duration of this period depends on the circumstances of the woman.

The primary purpose of iddat is to:

- Allow the woman sufficient time to mourn the death of her husband.
- Protect her dignity by preventing social criticism related to immediate remarriage.
- Determine whether she is pregnant, so that the paternity of a child, if any, can be clearly established.

Duration of Iddat and Its Legal Implications

1. In cases of divorce, a Muslim woman is required to observe iddat for a period of three months. According to the husband’s argument in the Shah Bano case, maintenance was payable only during this period, after which no further obligation existed.
2. In cases of the husband’s death, the iddat period extends to four lunar months and ten days, irrespective of whether the marriage was consummated.

3. If the woman is pregnant, the iddat period continues until the birth of the child. This provision is significant because it establishes that iddat is connected to biological and social considerations rather than long-term financial security.

4. If a woman is pregnant at the time of her husband's death, the waiting period may extend through the entire duration of pregnancy, ensuring certainty of paternity.

Judgement of the case

The Shah Bano case judgment was passed on April 23, 1985, by a five-judge Supreme Court bench led by Chief Justice Y.V. Chandrachud, with the other judges being Justices Ranganath Misra, D.A. Desai, O. Chinnappa Reddy, and E.S. Venkataramiah.

The Hon'ble Supreme Court held that Section 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code, 1973 applies to all women, irrespective of their religion. The Court clarified that Section 125 is a secular provision, enacted to prevent vagrancy and destitution, and therefore cannot be restricted by personal laws. While examining the alleged conflict between Section 125 CrPC and Muslim Personal Law, the Court observed that Section 125 forms part of the Criminal Procedure Code and not any personal law.

As a result, every husband, regardless of his religion, is legally obligated to provide maintenance to his wife if she is unable to maintain herself, and this obligation continues until the wife remarries. The Supreme Court further held that mahr (dower) is not a substitute for maintenance after divorce. It explained that mahr is an amount paid as a consideration for marriage and serves as a symbol of respect and security for the wife under Muslim Personal Law, rather than an amount payable upon divorce. Therefore, even if a Muslim husband has paid the full amount of mahr, it does not absolve him of his responsibility to provide maintenance to his divorced wife. Accordingly, the Court rejected the husband's contention and directed him to pay maintenance to Shah Bano Begum under Section 125 CrPC until she remarries, thereby reinforcing the principles of gender justice, equality, and constitutional morality.

Conclusion

The Shah Bano case is a landmark judgment that clarified the relationship between personal laws and secular statutory provisions in India. The Supreme Court firmly held that Section 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code applies to all women irrespective of religion, and that a divorced Muslim woman is entitled to maintenance beyond the iddat period if she is unable to

maintain herself. The Court also ruled that mahr or dower is not a substitute for post-divorce maintenance. It brought into sharp relief the tension between personal laws and constitutional guarantees, drawing attention to the importance of Uniform Civil Code in the country mentioned in the [Article 44 of the Indian Constitution](#).